

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

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Abstract. This article analyzes opinions about the use of innovative technologies in the educational process based on primary sources. This article can be used by researchers

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Today, it is important to carry out the activities of every sector and system based on innovative ideas and technologies. In this regard, before entering the topic, we found it necessary to dwell a little on the meaning of the word "innovation". The concept of innovation (Latin novus new) began to be used in research and scientific work in the 19th century. First, it represented the introduction of individual elements from one field to another. By learning the laws of introducing technical innovations, companies have mastered "innovation policy" as a whole system for profit. This activity has general features, rules, and a mechanism for updating the voluntary part of society's life. Innovative technologies are innovations and changes in the activities of teachers and students in the pedagogical process, and require the use of interactive methods in its implementation. Interactive methods are based on the activity of each student participating in the educational process, free and independent thinking. [1.25] When using these methods, learning becomes an interesting activity for the student. When interactive methods are used, students acquire the skills and abilities to work independently with the help and cooperation of teachers. Pupils acquire new knowledge on the basis of scientific research, research, experimental tests. The principle of gaining knowledge through science is followed. Participants of the educational process work in small groups. Assignments are not given to individual students, but to all members of a small group. The main form of organizing the teaching process is the lesson. [2.9] Currently, various non-traditional forms of teaching are being introduced. Such lessons serve to develop the student's creative abilities, strengthen his intellectual potential, expand his scientific worldview, and develop the skills and abilities to quickly and fully accept every new thing. The use of innovative technologies in the course of the lesson arouses interest in scientific research in students, develops creativity and creativity. As a result, acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are applied in practical activities, the quality

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of learning increases. For this, the teacher should be skilled and properly plan the lesson according to the content of the topics, and make all the students work actively and consciously during the training. [5.25] Pedagogical innovation is innovation in pedagogical practice, changes in the content and technology of teaching and education, aimed at increasing their efficiency. Innovation is understood as the result of innovation, and the innovation process is considered as the development of three main stages: creation of an idea (in a certain case, scientific research), the development of ideas in practical aspects and the implementation of innovations. [3.30] Optimality, as a measure of the effectiveness of pedagogical innovation, requires the effort of teachers and students to achieve a guaranteed result. Different teachers and students have different levels of effectiveness in their personal pedagogical and educational activities. In addition, the effectiveness of specific, correct pedagogical (for example, methodological) innovations will be much lower if they are not supported in the socio-pedagogical plan. Thus, the creation of a socio-pedagogical context that supports private innovations and socio-pedagogical innovations can significantly enhance the development of the regional education system as a whole. In addition to the above, it is easy to see structures such as innovation creation and innovation (absorption) in any innovation process; a complex innovation process that underlies the development of the entire school, consisting of interrelated micro-innovation processes. An important pedagogical condition for the formation of creativity in teachers is to direct it to independent learning and creative thinking. In addition, it is necessary to pay special attention to creative environment, specific moral and spiritual condition, organizational, methodical and psychological measures among teachers. they achieve. This is why it determines the level of optimality of pedagogical innovations. [1.9] Effectiveness as the most important sign of innovative methods is manifested only when positive achievements are achieved in the teacher's activity. The technological, observability, and recording of results in measurements is demonstrated by evaluating new methods and methods of teaching. The important aspect of this measure is manifested in the unity of the formation of a person, his perceptions and concepts. In this regard, the innovative process can be considered as the process of bringing the scientific idea to the stage of practical use and making changes in the related social and pedagogical environment. The activity that ensures the transformation of ideas into innovation and forms the management system of this process is an innovative activity. There is another distinctive feature of the innovation process development stages. The creative application of pedagogical innovations in pedagogical experience is manifested at the initial stage of the work of individual teachers. [3,21] It is important to inculcate the content of pedagogical innovations

and the methods of its application into the experience of future teachers . In order to bring pedagogical innovations into the life of the educational institution on a large scale , it is necessary to create an environment of innovation, to form a certain moral and psychological state, to use organizational, methodical, and psychological measures. For this purpose, it is necessary to develop the creative functions of future listeners, consistently arm them with pedagogical innovations, and teach them to analyze and apply innovative methods . [7.15] In the science of pedagogy, issues of innovation in the educational system are constantly being studied by specialists . However, socio-pedagogical innovations as a factor in the development of the regional education system, on the one hand, due to the relatively recent emergence of the rapidly developing social pedagogy as a field of science and practical activity , on the other hand, the relative social tendency of education decentralization and regionalization related to novelty.

Lessons organized on the basis of pedagogical technologies should meet the needs of the student according to organizational methods and delivery methods. Because such lessons are closer to the child's psyche . Achieving the goal is motivation based on the stimulation of students ' interest, desire and desire to learn learning materials, and this is the internal rapprochement of the teacher and students. [2.110]

Innovative technologies in education allow to regulate learning and direct it in the right direction . People have always been afraid of the unknown, and they have reacted negatively to any changes. Stereotypes that exist in the public mind , affect the usual way of life, lead to painful events, and prevent the renewal of all types of education. The reason why people do not want to accept innovations in modern education is because they block the vital needs for comfort, security and self-affirmation. Innovative behavior does not mean adaptation , it implies the formation of one's own personality, self-development. The teacher should understand that innovative education is a way of educating a well-rounded person. "Ready-made templates" are not suitable for him, it is important to constantly improve his intellectual level. A teacher freed from " complexes" and psychological barriers is ready to be a full participant in innovative changes. One of the tasks of the modern school is to reveal the possibilities of all participants of the pedagogical process , to provide them with opportunities to show their creative abilities. Solving these problems is not possible without implementing the variability of educational processes, in connection with which there are various innovative types and types of educational institutions that require deep scientific and practical understanding. News or innovations what kind of professional human activity is characteristic and therefore naturally becomes an object of study, analysis and implementation.

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Innovations do not appear by themselves, they are the scientific research of individual teachers and whole teams, advanced pedagogy is the result of experience.

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